

INITIATE²

INFECTIOUS DISEASE TREATMENT MODULE

Mockup Testing Guide

Goals for Mock-Up Testing

Goals:

1. To validate the dimension and configuration of the space to inform the design of the unit, through testing the following design principles:
 - a. Contact enabling design
 - b. Accessibility and inclusiveness
 - c. Usability
2. To validate the flow of the unit to inform the design of the unit
3. To see how long it takes to conduct the mock-up testing

Mockup grid

How to use this questionnaire and grid

The grid design in this slide represents the physical layout of the low resolution prototype when it will be set up for the mock-up testing.

Each question for the design principles includes this grid design, and certain sections have been highlighted where relevant to guide the testing.

During the mock-up testing, you will use this grid to mark the answers for the questions in each of the design principles (e.g. where there is visibility between patient and staff).

Each question also has a section for open comments/observations where you can write down notes from each test.

MOCK UP TESTING PLAN

DESIGN PRINCIPLE 1
CONTACT ENABLING DESIGN

Question Checklist

Design Principle: Contact Enabling Design

- 1. Visual contact in between patient and visitor is enabled when patient is in bed.
- 2. Visual contact in between patient and visitor is enabled when patient is outside the room.
- 3. Visual contact in between staff and patients is enabled when patient is in bed and staff in the staff area.
- 4. Visual contact in between staff and patients is enabled when patient is outside the room and staff in the staff area.
- 5. Visual contact in between staff members is enabled regardless of staff's location in the high risk area.

Contact Enabling Design - Question 1

HYPOTHESIS: visual contact in between patient and visitor is enabled when **patient is in bed**.

DESCRIPTION: the patient is located in J9/J10 (red). Visitor moves in the yellow zone (51 cells) from O1 to A1, from A1 to A16.

INDICATOR: Cells with direct visual contact

OUTPUT: $\% = (\text{number of cells with visibility}/30) \times 100$

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Contact Enabling Design - Question 2

HYPOTHESIS: visual contact in between patient and visitor is enabled when **patient is outside the room**.

DESCRIPTION: the patient is located in F8/F9 (red). Visitor moves in the yellow zone (30 cells) from O1 to A1, from A1 to A16.

INDICATOR: Cells with direct visual contact

OUTPUT: $\% = (\text{number of cells with visibility}/30) \times 100$

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Contact Enabling Design - Question 3

HYPOTHESIS: visual contact in between staff and patients is enabled when **patient is in bed and staff in the staff area.**

DESCRIPTION: the patient is located in J9/J10 (red).
Staff moves:

- in the green zone (37 cells) from N13 to N7, as shown in the image.

INDICATOR: Cells with direct visual contact

OUTPUT: $\% = (\text{number of cells with visibility} / 39) \times 100$

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Contact Enabling Design - Question 4

HYPOTHESIS: visual contact in between staff and patients is enabled when **patient is outside the room and staff in the staff area.**

DESCRIPTION: the patient is located in F8/F9 (red).
Staff moves:

- in the green zone (37 cells) from N13 to N7, as shown in the image.

INDICATOR: Cells with direct visual contact

OUTPUT: $\% = (\text{number of cells with visibility}/39) \times 100$

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Contact Enabling Design - Question 5

HYPOTHESIS: visual contact in between staff members is enabled regardless of staff's location in the high risk area.

DESCRIPTION:

The staff A is located in the staff area (L9) and walk back and forward on the red arrow. Staff B moves:

- in the green zone (36 cells) from O4 to K14 as per drawing

INDICATOR: Cells with direct visual contact

OUTPUT: $\% = (\text{number of cells with visibility}/69) \times 100$

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Result Summary - Design Principle 2

QUESTION	% INDICATOR RESULT	COMMENTS
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		

DESIGN PRINCIPLE 2
ACCESSIBILITY AND INCLUSIVENESS

Question Checklist

Design Principle: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

- 1. Adequate space for special needs patients requiring a wheelchair
- 2. Adequate space and characteristics to transport a patient on a stretcher
- 3. Adequate space for a wheelchair to enter into the toilet space, and rotate within the toilet space (including sink and latrine)
- 4. Rapid accessibility for staff to enter the red zone and the room in case of emergency

Accessibility and Inclusiveness - Question 1

HYPOTHESIS: There is adequate space to enter the module for special needs patients requiring a wheelchair.

DESCRIPTION:

- Time how long it takes to enter the red area with a wheelchair from the entrance of the module
- Try moving a wheelchair around internal area

INDICATOR:

- The timing of each section on graph
- Number of cells with adequate space for a wheelchair

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Accessibility and Inclusiveness - Question 2

HYPOTHESIS: There is adequate space and characteristics to transport a patient on a stretcher

DESCRIPTION:

- Time how long it takes to enter the red area with a stretcher from the entrance of the module
- Try moving a stretcher around internal area

INDICATOR:

- The timing of each section on graph
- Number of cells with adequate space for a stretcher

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Accessibility and Inclusiveness - Question 3

HYPOTHESIS: There is adequate space for a wheelchair to enter into the toilet space, and rotate within the toilet space (including sink and latrine)

DESCRIPTION: Try entering the toilet (cells G7, G8, H7, H8) with a wheelchair, and rotate within the toilet space as would be required

INDICATOR: Mark the cells where there is adequate space in the toilet area entrance and room

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Accessibility and Inclusiveness - Question 4

HYPOTHESIS: There is rapid accessibility for staff to enter the red zone and the room in case of emergency

DESCRIPTION: A staff in the staff area is requested to wear a full ebola PPE and walk to the patient's bed. Donning time is not considered and time-keeping begins when donning is completed.

INDICATOR: The amount of time needed to complete task in the description (time to be multiplied to account for more modules)

OPEN COMMENTS/OBSERVATIONS:

Result Summary - Design Principle 2

QUESTION	% INDICATOR RESULT	COMMENTS
1		
2		
3		
4		

DESIGN PRINCIPLE 3

USABILITY

Design Principle 3

Design Principle 3 has two components for testing:

1. Scenario testing
2. Static tests

Instructions:

- Go through the two scenarios highlighted in this section
- Use the results and feedback from these scenarios to gather and complete the feedback for the on **Usability Questions**

Overview of scenarios for testing:

Scenario 1

Patient is attended and treated in real-time within critical incidents

Scenario 2

ITDM is adaptable for all age groups (i.e. Newborn - Children - Adult - Elderly) with their special needs. Visual and physical (i. e. In wall integrated gloves) contact to relatives is possible

Further instructions on how to run the scenario are outlined below.

1. SCENARIO TESTING

Scenario 1 - Instructions 1/2

 <small>Patient information</small>	<p>Ernst Meier</p>	<p>Age Height Weight</p>	<p>46 y 185 cm 75 kg</p>	<p>Specials:</p>
 <small>Briefing</small>	<p>Patient is isolated in the unit with confirmed infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission) on day 5 in quarantine. During lunch, the patient shows signs of difficulty in breathing.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p>			
 <small>Information for instructors</small>	<p>Patient develops an allergic reaction to nuts in the meal he is eating. Rapid progress with respiratory distress and hypotension. No staff in the red area, needs to be donned before accessing the patient, medication needs to be provided to red zone</p>			
 <small>Hot Seats</small>	<p>2x Nurse (Nurse 1 M8 (red area), Nurse 2 green area) 1x Physician (green area)</p>			
 <small>Instructor team</small>	<p>2x Simulationinstructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse</p>			
 <small>Scenario issues</small>	<p>Anaphylactic reaction with obstructed airway / circulatory problems</p>			
 <small>Learning objectives</small>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Medical Management kits are used correctly 			

Scenario 1 - Instructions 2/2

 Material / Simulationequipment	Room	Patient / Simulator		Gimmicks/Requisites																														
 Simulation Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isolation Unit Stretcher / Bed Vital parameter monitor Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway i.v. / infusion / ampoule kit (adrenalin, corticoide) Emergency pack 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient Simulator (SimMan 3G) or actor (+ Intubation mannequin) i.v. cannula / infusion right forearm 	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Start settings</th> <th>Process</th> <th>Under therapy</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ECG Sr</td> <td>Sr</td> <td>Sr</td> </tr> <tr> <td>HF 110 /min</td> <td>160 /min</td> <td>120 /min</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SpO₂ 93 %</td> <td>85 %</td> <td>91 %</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BP 140/ 90 mmHg</td> <td>70 / 50 mmHg</td> <td>90 / 50 mmHg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>etCO₂ 40 mmHg</td> <td>30 mmHg</td> <td>30 mmHg</td> </tr> <tr> <td>RespR 20 /min</td> <td>35 /min</td> <td>/min</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temp. 37,8 °C</td> <td>37,8 °C</td> <td>°C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>BloodSug 102 mg/dl</td> <td>102 mg/dl</td> <td>mg/dl</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pupils 3 mm / 3 mm , LR + / +</td> <td>4 mm / 4 mm , LR + / +</td> <td>mm / mm , LR /</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Start settings	Process	Under therapy	ECG Sr	Sr	Sr	HF 110 /min	160 /min	120 /min	SpO ₂ 93 %	85 %	91 %	BP 140/ 90 mmHg	70 / 50 mmHg	90 / 50 mmHg	etCO ₂ 40 mmHg	30 mmHg	30 mmHg	RespR 20 /min	35 /min	/min	Temp. 37,8 °C	37,8 °C	°C	BloodSug 102 mg/dl	102 mg/dl	mg/dl	Pupils 3 mm / 3 mm , LR + / +	4 mm / 4 mm , LR + / +	mm / mm , LR /	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 3x Lunch <p>Anamnesis</p> <p>S Dyspnea since lunch</p> <p>A Allergic to nuts</p> <p>M -</p> <p>P -</p> <p>L 5 minutes ago</p> <p>E -</p> <p>R -</p>
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 Scenario Saver	<p>Lungsound: Obstruction</p> <p>Patient shows signs of dyspnea, coughing, obstruction.</p> <p>Rapid progress with beginning altered mental status (GCS 8) due to hypotension.</p> <p>Too easy: progress of airway swelling with difficult airway (need for surgical airway)</p> <p>Too difficult: fast response to adrenalin and mild anaphylaxis</p>																																	
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Criteria to identify a critical ill patient Patient is attended within adequate time <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time needed for donning the PPE and begin of treatment Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time Medical Management kits are used correctly 																																	

Scenario 2 - Instructions 1/2

 <small>Patient information</small>	Jonathan Schmid		Age 12 m Height 85 cm Weight 10 kg	Specials:
 <small>Briefing</small>	<p>Patient is brought to the isolation unit together with his mother, both suspect of infection with pathogen X (airborne transmission). Since 2 days dyspnea and coughing.</p> <p>Patient history: no pre-existing conditions Medication: no medication</p> <p>1 Nurse with PPE in the isolation unit</p>			
 <small>Information for instructors</small>	<p>Within triage the patient's status worsens with altered mental status and progressing signs of dyspnea.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypoxia due to infection of lower airways • Hypotension due to septic shock 			
 <small>Hot Seats</small>	<p>2x Nurse (1x with PPE in isolation unit) 1x Physician</p>			
 <small>Instructor team</small>	<p>2x Simulationinstructor 1x Technician 1x SimNurse 1x Actor (mother)</p>			
 <small>Scenario Issues</small>	<p>2 Organ dysfunction (Hypoxia and septic shock) in pediatric patient</p>			
 <small>Learning objectives</small>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical incident is identified quickly • Patient is attended within adequate time • Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time • Medical Management kits are used correctly 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standard care can be provided to all patient groups • Visibility and physical contact is possible • Evaluation of unit-space for treatment of 2 patients (mother + child) 	

Scenario 2 - Instructions 2/2

 Material / Simulation equipment	Room <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vital parameter monitor Defibrillator Oxygen / Airway (Children) i.v. / infusion / ampoule kit (for children) 	Patient / Simulator <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patient Simulator (SimBaby) and actor (mother) 			Gimmicks/Requisites <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal Protective Equipment 3x 																																																
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 Scenario Saver	Too easy: Getting comatose -> need for intubation Too difficult: getting better when given i.v. volume																																																				
 Specials / Debriefing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical ill pediatric patient is identified quickly <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scores / signs of critical ill pediatric patients Patient is attended within adequate time <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Without risk of self-endangerment of staff Adequate treatment is provided in adequate time <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Treatment of hypoxia and hypovolemia Medical Management kits are used correctly Visibility and physical contact is possible Evaluation of unit-space for treatment of 2 patients (mother + child) 																																																				

Scenario Follow Up Questions

Ask the following questions after running the scenarios to develop a deeper understanding around the challenges and potential improvements found in the mock up.

QUESTIONS: Mark on scale using the scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect

1. Was the space enough to work on the patient? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

2. Was it possible to attend the patient in an adequate time? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

Scenario Follow Up Questions

3. What worked or didn't work when performing emergency procedures on the patient from the green zone using the glove box?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

4. Was the transparent screen helpful for your medical procedures? How?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

Scenario Follow Up Questions

5. Was the transparent screen helpful to respond to sudden emergency from the green zone? How?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

6. Was it possible for the staff to work in a safe environment? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

Scenario Follow Up Questions

7. Was it possible to provide all medical procedures needed in a qualitative adequate way? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

8. Was it possible to provide all medical procedure in a quantitative adequate way? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

Scenario Follow Up Questions

9. Did you miss any tools to attend the patient well? What were they?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

10. Did you miss any structural part to attend the patient well? What were they?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

Scenario Follow Up Questions

11. Did the patient feel well-treated (if actors are used)? Why/why not?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10				

COMMENTS:

2. STATIC TESTS

Question Checklist

Design Principle: Usability

- 1. Spacing, pathways and arrangements are adequate in the patient room when all of the equipment and patients are in the room
- 2. Overall staff/patient safety in the space in terms of movement in the treatment model (includes green & red areas)
- 3. How is the flow of staff movement after initial orientation of staff
- 4. How is the flow of patient movement after initial orientation of staff
- 5. How is the flow of visitor movement after initial orientation of staff
- 6. Staff have the ability to do basic manipulation from the green zone to the red zone
- 7. Staff have the ability to do medical procedures whilst within the red zone

Usability - Question 1

HYPOTHESIS: Put the patient & all equipment (from WHO list) together and see if all the spacing, pathways and arrangements are adequate in the patient room

DESCRIPTION: Simulate patient health emergency and medical staff consequent set of actions

INDICATOR: How effective was the spacing, pathways and arrangements?
(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 2

HYPOTHESIS: Overall staff/patient safety in the space in terms of movement in the treatment model (includes green & red areas)

DESCRIPTION: Simulate staff and patient movements within and from/to red and green areas, and check for potential movement impediments, especially those who might cause safety issue (like contaminations etc.) E.g. obstacles, bottlenecks

INDICATOR: How safe was the movement in the treatment module
(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 3

HYPOTHESIS: How is the flow of staff movement after orientation of staff? E.g. intuitiveness and wayfinding

DESCRIPTION: Staff to run across the whole IDTM, internally and externally.

INSTRUCTIONS: Brief on what to touch/not touch, use the grid design for briefing if needed, and add marks on the floor in mock-up to mark or

INDICATOR: How effective was the wayfinding and intuitiveness of the space?
(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 4

HYPOTHESIS: How is the flow of patient movement after initial orientation of staff

DESCRIPTION: The patient is able to clearly understand where they can move around

INDICATOR: How effective was the wayfinding and flow for patients?

(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 5

HYPOTHESIS: How is the flow of visitor movement after initial orientation of staff

DESCRIPTION: The visitor is able to clearly understand where to move around the yellow area

INDICATOR: How effective was the wayfinding and flow for visitors?

(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 6

HYPOTHESIS: Staff have the ability to do basic manipulation from the green zone to the red zone

DESCRIPTION: Simulate patient manipulation from green area (use scenario 1).

INDICATOR: How effective does the design enable manipulation of patients from green to red zone?
(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

Usability - Question 7

HYPOTHESIS: Staff have the ability to do medical procedures whilst within the red zone

DESCRIPTION: Staff to manipulate patient from all 4 bed sides (use scenario 1)

INDICATOR: How effectively can staff conduct medical procedures whilst in the red zone?
(Mark on scale: 1 = completely ineffective, 10 = perfect)

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 10

EXPLAIN ANY ISSUES & THE REASON / OPEN COMMENTS:

OVERALL COMMENTS

OPEN COMMENTS/IDEAS

COMMENTS

IDEAS

NEEDS TO BE CONSIDERED

NEEDS

INITIATE²

INFECTIOUS DISEASE TREATMENT MODULE